

Major insect pests of rainfed wetland rice in tropical Asia

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Rice is a highly adaptable crop and is cultivated over a wide range of environments. Rice culture is classified on the basis of water availability into four major environments: 1) deep water, 2) irrigated wetland, 3) rainfed wetland, and 4) dryland. Within tropical Asia, rice entomology research has concentrated is on irrigated wetland and dryland environments, and little attention has been given to deepwater and rainfed wetland environments.

Recent statistics show that the rainfed wetland environment occupies 46% of the land area devoted to rice in Asia exclusive of the People's Republic of China. Within this classification rice usually grown as a single crop during the monsoon season and is subject to periodic and unpredictable drought and flooding. These areas are typified by a distinct rice-free dry season. The extreme variations in rainfall and growing season profoundly affect rice insect pests. The fact that rice fields are flooded during part of the growing season eliminates many soil-inhabiting pests common to dryland environments. A survey of the rice entomologists in eight Asian countries yielded a list of insect pests common to rainfed wetland environments in the region. Most important were yellow rice borer, rice gall midge, rice leaf folder, rice bug, and rice caseworm, which are also major pests of irrigated wetland environments, but, with the exception of rice bug and rice leaf folder, not of dryland environments. Thirty other pest species were important on a country-to-country basis. Because of the locational intermingling of rainfed and irrigated environments, it is difficult to state that a pest is indigenous to rainfed wetland environments. For example, the brown planthopper is capable of migrating long distances and may disperse to rainfed environments from nearby irrigated areas. Only two pests are thought to be unique to rainfed wetland environments—the rice root weevil and white stem borer. These insects normally estivate and are culturally controlled if a second rice crop is grown in the dry season.

Insect pests of rainfed wetland rice in tropical Asia as determined by a survey of rice entomologists, 1978. ^{a/}									
Pest ^{b/}		Country ^{c/}							
Scientific name	Common name	Bangladesh	Burma	India	Indonesia	Malaysia	Philippines	Sri Lanka	Thailand
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (Walker)	Yellow rice borer	**	**	**			**		*
<i>S. innotata</i> (Walker)	White rice borer			*	**		**	0	
<i>S. nivella</i> (F.)	Top borer	0				0		0	*
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> (Walker)	Striped rice borer		*	*	*		*		*
<i>C. polychrysus</i> (Meyrick)	Dark-headed rice borer	*				*			**
<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walker)	Pink borer	*		*		*	*		
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	Rice gall midge	*		**	**	0	0	**	**
<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> Guenee	Rice caseworm	*	*	**	**	*	**	*	*
<i>Cnaphalocrosis medinalis</i> (Guenee)	Rice leaf folder	*		**	**	*	**	**	**
<i>Mythimna separata</i> (Walker)	Rice ear-cutting caterpillar	*	*	*	*		*		*
<i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> (Boisduval)	Rice swarming caterpillar			**				*	**
<i>Pelopidas mathias</i> (Fabricius)	Rice skipper			*					*
<i>Melanitis leda ismene</i> Cramer	Rice green-horned caterpillar			*			*		*
<i>Rivula atimeta</i> Swinhoe	Rice hairy caterpillar	0	0	0	0	0	*	0	0
<i>Susumia exiqua</i> (Butler)	Fijian leaf folder	0				0		0	*
<i>Leptocoris acuta</i> Thunberg	Rice bug	*	*		**		**	*	**
<i>L. oratorius</i> (Fabricius)	Rice bug	*	*		**	*	**	0	**
<i>Scotinophora coarctata</i> (Fabricius)	Malayan black rice bug					*		0	*
<i>S. lurida</i> (Burmester)	Japanese black rice bug							*	*
<i>Hieroglyphus banian</i> (Fabricius)	Large rice grasshopper			*	*	0			*
<i>Patanqa succincta</i> (Linnaeus)	Bombay locust	0		*	*			0	*
<i>Locusta migratoria manilensis</i> (Meyen)	Oriental migratory locust	0		*	*			0	*
<i>Oxya chinensis</i> (Thunberg)	Small rice grasshopper			*	*			0	*
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Distant)	Green rice leafhopper	*		*	*	*	*		*
<i>N. nigropictus</i> (Stal)	Green rice leafhopper	*		*	*		*		*
<i>Recilia dorsalis</i> (Motschulsky)	Zig-zag rice leafhopper			*				*	*
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	Brown rice planthopper			**	**	*		**	*
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horvath)	Whitebacked rice planthopper			*		*		*	*
<i>Hydrellia philippina</i>	Rice whorl maggot			*	*		**		
<i>Atherigona oryzae</i> (=exiqua) Stein	Rice shoot fly	*	*					*	
<i>Baliothrips bifomis</i> (Bagnall)	Rice thrips			*		0	0	**	*
<i>Brevennis rehi</i> (Lindinger)	Rice mealy bug			*		0		0	*
<i>Dictyospa armigera</i> (Oliver)	Rice hispa	*		*		0	0		*
<i>Echinocnemus oryzae</i> (Marshall)	Rice root weevil	0		*		0	0	0	

^{a/} Bangladesh (S. Alam, H.D. Catling, A.N.M. Rezaul Karim), Burma (U Mya Thwin), India (N. Panda, K.C. Mathur), Indonesia (I. Manwan, A. Kartohardjono, O. Mochida), Malaysia (G.S. Lim), Philippines (I.A. Litsinger), Sri Lanka (N. Wickremasinghe), Thailand (W. Katanyukul, S. Pongprasert).

^{b/} Pawar, A.D. 1975. The rice Entomology Newsletter No. 2. Updated by A.T. Barrion, Entomology Department, IRRI.

^{c/} ** =major insect (perennial yield losses of 5% in at least 1 major region within the country), * =minor pest (variable year-to-year infestations resulting in yield losses of 5% in at least 1 major region within a country), 0 =pest not recorded on rice from the country.